

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL DATA FOR 2-(ARYLSULFONYL)-ACETOPHENONES

No.	m.p. °C ^a	band A ^b		band B ^b		Neutral form ^d		Anion ^e	
		λ _{nm}	ε.10 ⁻³	λ _{nm}	ε.10 ⁻³	λ _{nm}	ε.10 ⁻³	λ _{nm}	ε.10 ⁻³
Ia	98	212	15.18	253	13.70	256	16.22	302	14.00
b	114	220	14.42	280	21.43	298	15.71	305	14.04
c	101	213	21.51	266	18.53	267	19.75	303	16.66
d	134	217	11.29	267	17.88	267	22.12	306	16.66
e	136	220	10.32	267	15.02	265	18.66	358	8.22
IIa	110	220	13.15	267	13.97	252	14.10	300	13.60
b	122	227	20.66	292	18.52	292	17.50	302	16.75
c	99	219	19.00	265	20.25	264	16.25	300	13.25
d	139	221	17.60	267	19.32	268	19.50	306	13.12
e	145	227	19.56	265	19.94	264	15.77	360	7.55
IIIa	119	220	23.99	254	17.20	265	23.50	304	13.00
				282c	24.11				
b	169	233	22.41	292	19.39	294	17.25	308	15.75
c	149	215	18.22	240	22.32	260	18.50	310	15.00
				263c	21.05				
d	164	239m	26.20	267	26.37	268	19.50	315	14.00
e	190	236m	—	265	—	238	17.40	322	8.00
IVa	129	—	—	252	23.30	250	21.00	367	6.25
b	258 ^h	226	14.29	252	14.03	265	18.50	365	5.75
				288c	13.18				
d	161	214	17.50	265	23.00	258	24.50	358	7.25
e	257	—	—	258	15.67	260	21.32	370	9.24

a : literature m.p. °C^{1, 16, 17} ; Ia (96), Ib (114), IIa (110), IVa (129), IVb (258), IVc (161), IVd (257).
 b : In ethanol.
 c : Band C
 d : In 60% (v/v) ethanol-water, pH 2-3.
 e : In 60% (v/v) ethanol-water, pH 11-12.
 m : masked.

TABLE 2—ENERGY OF C.T. BAND AND IONISATION CONSTANTS OF 2-(ARYLSULFONYL)-ACETOPHENONES

Compound	E _{CT} (ev)		pK _a [*]	pK _a	
	Calcd.	Observed		EtOH 0%	EtOH 100%
Ia	5.04	4.91	9.87	9.27	10.28
b	4.02	4.43	10.56	9.74	11.10
c	4.78	4.67	10.18	9.43	10.75
d	4.72	4.65	9.14	8.57	9.70
e	4.62	4.65	8.00	7.58	8.25
IIa	5.04	4.65	10.01	—	—
b	4.02	4.25	10.95	—	—
c	4.78	4.68	10.48	—	—
d	4.72	4.65	9.58	—	—
e	4.62	4.68	8.45	—	—
IIIa	5.04	4.88	9.43	—	—
b	4.02	4.25	9.91	—	—
c	4.78	4.72	9.87	—	—
d	4.72	4.65	8.94	—	—
e	4.62	4.68	7.77	—	—
IVa	5.04	4.93	8.63	—	—
b	4.02	4.31	9.47	—	—
d	4.72	4.69	7.99	—	—
e	4.62	4.81	6.61	—	—

*pK_a in 60% (v/v) EtOH, standard deviation ±0.01-0.02.

the basis that the SO₂ and CH₃ groups act as insulators for the two phenyl rings⁷. Thus, the possible transitions found through the molecule are mainly due to the phenyl rings and the benzoyl system. Examination of the spectra of the β-keto sulfones and those of the previously studied diphenyl sulfones shows that this band can be assigned to the ¹L_b ← ¹A state^{8,9}. The last band C, which appears in the spectra of IIIa, c and IVb at 282, 263 and 288 nm, respectively, may be attributed to the π-π* transition of the carbonyl group influenced by charge transfer originating from the

substituted phenyl ring, the carbonyl group being the electron acceptor. The π-π* nature of this band is supported by its high absorptivity and the appearance of the band in the spectra of the compounds in HCl solution. In the spectra of the remaining compounds the CT band interferes with the ¹L_b band. The CT can be represented as follows :

A convenient support for the charge transfer origin of this band can be obtained from the calculations of the energy of CT⁸⁻¹⁰ in Table 2. The calculated values of E_{CT} coincide fairly well, within reasonable limits, with those resulting from the experimental data, where X is a substituent with donor or acceptor character, indicating that the CT originates from the phenyl group influenced by the substituent X present.

UV spectra in 60% (v/v) ethanol-water medium of varying pH : The ionization constants (pK_a's) of I-IV were determined in 60% (v/v) ethanol-water medium of μ=0.1 at 30±0.1° using the spectrophotometric method. At pH < 8, each of the 2-(arylsulfonyl)-acetophenone studied shows an intense π-π* absorption band at 250-298 nm corresponding to the non-ionized form liable to exist in such solutions. Within the pH range of 8-10.5, two bands appear near 260 and 305 nm. In strong alkaline media, pH > 11, the carbanion ion shows an intense π-π* band in the region 300-370 nm. The spectra recorded at different pH values show

two isobestic points near 240 and 270 nm (Fig. 1). The absorbance at wavelengths corresponding to the bands of the neutral and the anion form shows a dependence on the pH of the solution. The resulting curve exhibits the shape of a dissociation curve of a monobasic acid (Fig. 2). The pK_a values calculated from the absorbance-pH data were correlated

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of 2-(phenylsulfonyl)-acetophenone (Ia) at different pH values. Ia $5.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ in 60% (v/v) ethanol-water, 30°. Run and pH: (1) 1.36; (2) 7.25; (3) 8.59; (4) 9.10; (5) 9.37; (6) 9.57; (7) 9.78; (8) 10.01; (9) 10.26; (10) 10.50; (11) 11.06; (12) 11.53; (13) 12.03; (14) 12.30.

Fig. 2. Dependence of absorbance of some 2-(arylsulfonyl)-acetophenone on pH. Compd. and nm: Ia (300); Ib (270); IIb (246); IIIe (360); III d (267); IIIe (354); IVa (252); IVe (366).

with the substituent constant $\sigma_{X,Y}$ and $\sigma^*_{XC_6H_4, YC_6H_4^{H^+}}$ applying the simple Hammett equation (1). The regression lines expressing such correlations for Ia-e follow the equations 3-6, respectively:

$$pK_{aX} = 9.83 - 2.44 \sigma_X \quad (r = 0.996, s = \pm 0.1) \quad (3)$$

$$pK_{aX} = 11.12 - 2.16 \sigma^*_{XC_6H_4} \quad (r = 0.974, s = \pm 0.59) \quad (4)$$

$$pK_{aY} = 9.80 - 1.48 \sigma_Y \quad (r = 0.996, s = \pm 0.07) \quad (5)$$

$$pK_{aY} = 11.37 - 2.03 \sigma^*_{YC_6H_4} \quad (r = \pm 0.968, s = \pm 0.57) \quad (6)$$

The value of the reaction parameter (1.48) for the base $Ar-SO_2-\bar{C}H-CO-ph$ indicates that this carbanion is less susceptible to the transmission of substituent constant than the anion $ph-SO_2-\bar{C}H-CO-Ar$ for which $\rho = 2.44$. On the other hand, the plots of pK_a values against σ_X , constants of series I-IV, give straight lines for which the slopes are almost the same within the limits of experimental error (Table 3). This indicates that

TABLE 3—SLOPES OF pK_a -HAMMETT AND TAFT SUBSTITUENT CONSTANTS RELATIONSHIPS AS OBTAINED FROM STATISTICAL TREATMENT

Series	Slope		Slope of pK_a - σ_X plots of Ia-e in ethanol	
	Hammett	Taft	EtOH vol%	slope
Ia-e	2.44	2.16	—	2.53
IIa-e	2.27	2.03	20	2.09
IIIa-e	2.26	1.92	40	2.92
IVa-e	2.38	2.38	60	2.44
Ia-IVa	1.48	1.31	80	2.72
Ib-IVb	1.57	1.26	100	3.28
Id-IVd	1.52	1.16		
Ie-IVe	1.62	1.66		

the substituent X influences the acid dissociation constant in a manner which is reasonably independent of the substituent Y. Moreover, the results of the effect of the substituent Y show but similar effects as shown in Table 3. This view for the effect of substitution was confirmed by plotting the sum of $pK_{aX} + pK_{aY}$ vs pK_{aXY} giving an excellent linear relationship (Fig. 3). The ionization constants for I-IV were correlated with the extended

Fig. 3. Correlation of pK_{aXY} of the disubstituted 2-(arylsulfonyl)-acetophenones with $pK_{aX} + pK_{aY}$ of the mono-substituted analogues.

Hammett equation (2) by multiple regression analysis¹³. The correlation of pK_a values with equation (2) may be justified in a manner similar to above. The $\sigma_{I,X}$ constants were taken from the collection of Taft and coworkers¹³; the $\sigma_{R,X}$ constants were obtained from the relation:

$$\sigma_{R,X} = \sigma_{P,X} - \sigma_{I,X} \quad (7)$$

The $\sigma_{P,X}$ constants were from the compilation of Ritchie and Sager¹⁴. The results of the correlation with equation (2) are presented in Table 4. The values of the multiple correlation coefficient of 0.996-0.999 indicate an excellent correlation.

TABLE 4—RESULTS OF CORRELATION WITH EQUATION (2)

Series	n	$-\alpha$	$-\beta$	h	R
Ia-e	5	1.970 ± 0.08	1.969 ± 0.31	9.873 ± 0.04	0.999
IIa-e	5	1.939 ± 0.04	2.423 ± 0.06	10.049 ± 0.08	0.999
IIIa-e	5	2.414 ± 0.04	2.471 ± 0.05	9.478 ± 0.05	0.998
IVa-e	4	2.704 ± 0.02	2.780 ± 0.03	8.632 ± 0.01	0.999
Ia-IVa	4	1.561 ± 0.02	1.179 ± 0.04	9.841 ± 0.04	0.997
Ib-IVb	4	1.877 ± 0.06	2.426 ± 0.03	10.537 ± 0.15	0.996
I-IIIc	3	1.575	1.823	10.186	
Id-IVd	4	1.639 ± 0.12	1.835 ± 0.09	7.173 ± 0.02	0.999
Ie-IVe	4	1.696 ± 0.01	2.737 ± 0.03	8.017 ± 0.03	0.999

n : number of points.

R : multiple correlation coefficient.

Effect of some organic solvents on pK_a : The variation of the spectra and pK_a values of Ia-e, IIa and IVa is accounted for in the light of the presence of different organic solvents. The rate at which the ionic form is produced is influenced by both the nature and amount of organic solvent present. The elimination of protons from all compounds studied decreases as the amount of solvent increases. The variation of pK_a with dielectric constant (D) in solvent mixtures is given by the relation¹⁵

$$pK_a = pK_o + \frac{0.43 Ne^2}{RT} \frac{Z_1 Z_2}{r_1 r_2} \left(\frac{1}{D} \right) \dots (8)$$

Fig. 4. Dependence of pK_a values of Ic, IIa, IVa and Ia-e on the dielectric constant of : (i) ethanol-, (ii) dioxane and (iii) isopropanol-water mixtures.

The plots of pK_a as a function of $1/D$ are not strictly linear relationships (Fig. 4). This indicates that the change in pK_a with the proportion of organic solvent, though mainly governed by the dielectric constant, are also influenced by solvent basicity and by the solvation of the solute by organic solvent molecules. The slopes of the straight lines correlating the pK_a values with the substituent constant at different percentage of ethyl alcohol are not the same (Table 3) which supports the above contention. The pK_a values in pure aqueous medium and 100% ethyl alcohol are obtained by extrapolation of pK_a -%vol ethyl alcohol relationship (Table 2).

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